

Preprints in the life sciences by numbers

A new preprint every 4 minutes

125,000 biomedical preprints posted in 2020.¹

240% growth in 2020

Preprints represented 8% of literature in PubMed, compared to 3.2% in 2019.¹

40+ preprint servers

Broad range of preprint servers available for life sciences, biomedical and clinical research.²

Over 100,000 citations

Biomedical preprints received 106,040 citations in 2020.³

Infographics by ASAPbio Fellows:

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ASAPbio

Find more information at [ASAPbio.org](https://asapbio.org)

Sources:

1. EuropePMC <https://europepmc.org/>
2. <https://asapbio.org/preprint-servers>

3. Dimensions database
<https://app.dimensions.ai/discover/publication>

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